
 ON AN INEQUALITY IN A 1970 PAPER OF R. L. GRAHAM

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Received: 12/31/20, Accepted: 2/1/21, Published: 8/23/21

Abstract

Having recently come across a 1970 paper of R. L. Graham about cube-numbering and its generalizations, we found that one proof uses an inequality about the summatory function of the sum of binary digits of integers. Graham gave a very elegant and somehow unexpected proof of this inequality. We propose a more “pedestrian” —and somehow more standard— proof of this inequality, as well as questions about possible generalizations.

– Dedicated to the memory of Ron Graham

1. Introduction

R. L. Graham, in a study of cube-numbering and generalizations [6] used a curious inequality for the summatory function of the sum of binary digits which we now describe. Let $w(k)$ be the number of 1’s in the binary expansion of the integer k . Let $W(n) := \sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} w(k)$. Then, for all n_1, n_2 with $0 < n_1 \leq n_2$,

$$W(n_1 - 1) + W(n_2 - 1) + n_1 < W(n_1 + n_2 - 1) + 1. \quad (1)$$

The very elegant proof of this inequality given by Graham uses the following lemma.

Lemma 1 (Graham [6]). *Let r and s be nonnegative integers. If φ is a one-to-one map from $[0, r]$ to $[s, s + r]$, define*

$$\delta(\varphi) := \min_{0 \leq k \leq r} \{w(\varphi(k)) - w(k)\}.$$

Then

- (i) *There exists φ such that $\delta(\varphi) \geq 0$.*
- (ii) *If $s > r$, then there exists φ such that $\delta(\varphi) \geq 1$.*

The proof of this lemma and of the fact that it implies Inequality (1) can be found in [6] —but also see [7]. We could not guess how Graham had the idea of this lemma. Thus we wondered whether there could be a more direct, possibly “pedestrian”, proof. The point is that the sum of digit sequence (sequence A000120 in [10]), hence its summatory function (sequence A000788 in [10]), are 2-regular sequences in the sense of [1, 2]. Recall that a sequence $(u(n))_{n \geq 0}$ is called 2-regular if the \mathbb{Z} -module generated by its 2-kernel (i.e., the set of subsequences $\{(u(2^k n + a))_{n \geq 0}, k \geq 0, a \in [0, 2^k - 1]\}$) is a finitely generated \mathbb{Z} -module. In our case, this is just a consequence of the fact that $(w(2n))_{n \geq 0}$ and $(w(2n + 1))_{n \geq 0}$ are linear combinations of the sequence $(w(n))_{n \geq 0}$ and the constant sequence $(1)_{n \geq 0}$. Namely, for all $n \geq 0$, we have $w(2n) = w(n)$ and $w(2n + 1) = w(n) + 1$. These equalities imply equalities of a similar type for $W(n)$, and will be the basis of our proof.

2. Proof of Graham’s Inequality (1)

First we rewrite Inequality (1) as: for all (n_1, n_2) with $1 \leq n_1 \leq n_2$,

$$W(n_1 - 1) + W(n_2 - 1) + n_1 < W(n_1 + n_2 - 1) + 1.$$

Defining $m := n_1 - 1$ and $n := n_2 - 1$, Inequality (1) is equivalent to Inequality (2): for all (m, n) with $0 \leq m \leq n$,

$$W(m) + W(n) + m < W(m + n + 1). \tag{2}$$

Lemma 2. *The following equalities hold:*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for all } n \geq 1, \quad W(2n) &= W(n) + W(n - 1) + n \\ \text{for all } n \geq 0, \quad W(2n + 1) &= 2W(n) + n + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(m, n) := W(m + n + 1) - W(m) - W(n) - m$. Then the following equalities hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } n \geq 0, \quad A(n, n) &= 1 \text{ (hence Inequality (2) is sharp)} \\ \text{for } m \geq 1 \text{ and } n \geq 1, \quad A(2m, 2n) &= A(m - 1, n) + A(m, n - 1) \\ \text{for } m \geq 0 \text{ and } n \geq 1, \quad A(2m + 1, 2n) &= A(m, n) + A(m, n - 1) - 1 \\ \text{for } m \geq 1 \text{ and } n \geq 0, \quad A(2m, 2n + 1) &= A(m, n) + A(m - 1, n) - 1 \\ \text{for } m \geq 0 \text{ and } n \geq 0, \quad A(2m + 1, 2n + 1) &= 2A(m, n) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We write, for $\ell \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} W(2\ell) = \sum_{k=0}^{2\ell} w(k) &= \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} w(2j) + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell-1} w(2j + 1) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} w(j) + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell-1} (w(j) + 1) \\ &= W(\ell) + W(\ell - 1) + \ell \end{aligned}$$

and, for $\ell \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} W(2\ell + 1) &= \sum_{k=0}^{2\ell+1} w(k) = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} w(2j) + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} w(2j + 1) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} w(j) + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (w(j) + 1) \\ &= 2W(\ell) + \ell + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Using these relations for $W(2\ell)$ and $W(2\ell + 1)$, we obtain successively:

$$\text{For all } n \geq 0, A(n, n) = W(2n + 1) - 2W(n) - n = 1$$

and the following relations.

- For all (m, n) with $m \geq 1, n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} A(2m, 2n) &= W(2m + 2n + 1) - W(2m) - W(2n) - 2m \\ &= 2W(m + n) - W(m) - W(m - 1) \\ &\quad - W(n) - W(n - 1) - 2m + 1 \\ &= A(m - 1, n) + A(m, n - 1). \end{aligned}$$

- For all (m, n) with $m \geq 0, n \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} A(2m + 1, 2n) &= W(2m + 2n + 2) - W(2m + 1) - W(2n) - 2m - 1 \\ &= W(m + n + 1) + W(m + n) - 2W(m) \\ &\quad - W(n) - W(n - 1) - 2m - 1 \\ &= A(m, n) + A(m, n - 1) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

- For all (m, n) with $m \geq 1, n \geq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} A(2m, 2n + 1) &= W(2m + 2n + 2) - W(2m) - W(2n + 1) - 2m \\ &= W(m + n + 1) + W(m + n) - W(m) \\ &\quad - W(m - 1) - 2W(n) - 2m \\ &= A(m, n) + A(m - 1, n) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

- For all (m, n) with $m \geq 0, n \geq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} A(2m + 1, 2n + 1) &= W(2m + 2n + 3) - W(2m + 1) - W(2n + 1) - 2m - 1 \\ &= 2W(m + n + 1) - 2W(m) - 2W(n) - 2m - 1 \\ &= 2A(m, n) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

□

Now we are ready to prove the following proposition which is the result of Graham described above.

Proposition. *Inequality (1) holds.*

Proof. As we have seen, it suffices to prove Inequality (2), namely for all (m, n) with $0 \leq m \leq n$, one has

$$W(m) + W(n) + m < W(m + n + 1).$$

We will prove the statement (\mathcal{H}_n) :

$$(\mathcal{H}_n) : \quad \text{for all } m \in [0, n], \quad A(m, n) = W(m + n + 1) - W(m) - W(n) - m > 0.$$

We will actually check that (\mathcal{H}_0) holds, and prove that, if (\mathcal{H}_r) holds for all $r \in [0, n]$, then (\mathcal{H}_{2n}) and (\mathcal{H}_{2n+1}) hold. Note that (\mathcal{H}_0) holds trivially. Now suppose that, for some $n \geq 0$, (\mathcal{H}_r) holds for all $r \in [0, n]$, i.e., $A(q, r) > 0$ for all $r \in [0, n]$ and for all $q \in [0, r]$. We look at $A(k, 2n)$ and $A(k, 2n + 1)$ for $k \leq 2n$, resp. $k \leq 2n + 1$.

- $A(k, 2n)$

We can (and will) suppose that $n > 0$.

- If $k \in [0, 2n]$ is even, say $k = 2\ell$, we may suppose that $k \in [1, 2n - 1]$, since the case $k = 0$ is trivial, and the case $k = n$ is deduced from $A(2n, 2n) = 1$ as seen above. Thus $\ell \in [1, n - 1]$. We have

$$A(k, 2n) = A(2\ell, 2n) = A(\ell - 1, n) + A(\ell, n - 1) > 0$$

using first Lemma 2, then the induction hypothesis.

- If $k \in [0, 2n]$ is odd, say $k = 2\ell + 1$, we have that $k \in [1, 2n - 1]$. Thus $\ell \in [0, n - 1]$. We have

$$A(k, 2n) = A(2\ell + 1, 2n) = A(\ell, n) + A(\ell, n - 1) - 1 > 0$$

using first Lemma 2, then the induction hypothesis.

- $A(k, 2n + 1)$

- If $k \in [0, 2n + 1]$ is even, say $k = 2\ell$. We may suppose $k \neq 0$ since the case $k = 0$ is trivial. Then $\ell \in [1, n]$. Thus

$$A(k, 2n + 1) = A(2\ell, 2n + 1) = A(\ell, n) + A(\ell - 1, n) - 1 > 0$$

using first Lemma 2, then the induction hypothesis.

- If $k \in [0, 2n + 1]$ is odd, say $k = 2\ell + 1$. Thus $\ell \in [0, n]$. Thus

$$A(k, 2n + 1) = A(2\ell + 1, 2n + 1) = 2A(\ell, n) - 1 > 0$$

using first Lemma 2, then the induction hypothesis.

□

Remark 1. It is noted in [7] that $W(n) \leq \frac{1}{2}n \log_2 n$. Actually we know more: from [4] (also see [13]), we have $W(n) = \frac{1}{2}n \log_2 n + nF(\log_2 n)$, where F is a periodic, continuous, nowhere differentiable function with an absolutely convergent Fourier series. The function F , called the Trollope-Delange function, is closely related to the Takagi function [12] (see, e.g., [8, 9], and [11]). The evaluation of $W(n)$, F , and generalizations is still an active subject of research (see, e.g., [5]).

Remark 2. It is possible to obtain an upper bound for $A(m, n)$ by using the inequality $w(m + n) \leq w(m) + w(n)$ for all m, n . This inequality can be found, e.g., in a comment by Shevelev about sequence A000120 [10]. Namely one has $w(m) + w(n) - w(n + m) = v_2\binom{n+m}{n}$ which is a consequence of Legendre’s result [3, p. 10–12]: $w(n) = n - v_2(n!)$, where $v_2(k)$ is the 2-adic valuation of k . Hence

$$\begin{aligned} A(m, n) &= \sum_{j=0}^{m+n+1} w(j) - \sum_{j=0}^n w(j) - \sum_{j=0}^m w(j) - m \\ &= \sum_{j=n+1}^{m+n+1} w(j) - \sum_{j=0}^m w(j) - m = \sum_{j=0}^m w(j + n + 1) - \sum_{j=0}^m w(j) - m \\ &\leq \sum_{j=0}^m w(n + 1) - m = (m + 1)w(n + 1) - m. \end{aligned}$$

Note that this inequality is sharp (e.g., take $m = n = 2^k - 1$ for some $k \geq 1$).

3. Conclusion

A first possible generalization of this inequality is to replace base 2 with base $d \geq 2$, and w with the sum of digits in base d . But, since our proof essentially uses the 2-regularity of the sequence $(w(n))_{n \geq 0}$ and (thus) of its summatory function $(W(n))_{n \geq 0}$, one can ask whether some similar “super-superadditivity” result holds for summatory functions of all 2-regular (resp. d -regular) sequences. A more reasonable question could be whether summatory functions of pattern-counting sequences have such a property: the sequence $(w(n))_{n \geq 0}$ counts the number of 1’s in the binary expansion of n , thus one of the first examples to test would be the sequence $(u(n))_{n \geq 0}$ that counts the number of possibly overlapping blocks 11 in the binary expansion of n (this is sequence A014081 in [10]). The difficulty is then that, instead of having the relations $w(2n) = w(n)$ and $w(2n + 1) = w(n) + 1$, we have relations for a three-dimensional vector $z(n)$:

$$z(n) := \begin{pmatrix} u(n) \\ u(2n + 1) \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow z(2n) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} z(n), \quad z(2n + 1) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} z(n).$$

Acknowledgments. We would like to thank the referee for their pertinent remarks.

References

- [1] J.-P. Allouche, J. Shallit, The ring of k -regular sequences, *Theoret. Comput. Sci.* **98** (1992), 163–197.
- [2] J.-P. Allouche, J. Shallit, The ring of k -regular sequences, II, *Theoret. Comput. Sci.* **307** (2003), 3–29.
- [3] A.-M. Legendre, *Théorie des Nombres*, Firmin Didot Frères, Paris, 1830.
- [4] H. Delange, Sur la fonction sommatoire de la fonction “somme des chiffres”, *L’Ens. Math.* **21** (1975) 31–47.
- [5] O. E. Galkin, S. Yu. Galkina, Global extrema of the Delange function, estimations of digital sums and concave functions, *Mat. Sb.* **211** (2020), 32–70. Translated in *Sb. Math.* **211** (2020), 336–372.
- [6] R. L. Graham, On primitive graphs and optimal vertex assignments, *Ann. New York Acad.* **175** (1970), 170–186.
- [7] J. C. Jones, B. F. Torrence, The case of the missing case: the completion of a proof by R.L. Graham, *Pi Mu Epsilon J.* **10** (1999), 772–778.
- [8] M. Krüppel, Takagi’s continuous nowhere differentiable function and binary digital sums, *Rostock. Math. Kolloq.* **63** (2008), 37–54.
- [9] J. C. Lagarias, The Takagi function and its properties, in *Functions in Number Theory and their Probabilistic Aspects*, RIMS Kôkyûroku Bessatsu, B34, Res. Inst. Math. Sci. (RIMS), Kyoto, (2012), 153–189.
- [10] *On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, founded by N. J. A. Sloane. Electronically available at <https://oeis.org>.
- [11] T. Okada, T. Sekiguchi, Y. Shiota, Applications of binomial measures to power sums of digital sums, *J. Number Theory* **52** (1995), 256–266.
- [12] T. Takagi, A simple example of the continuous function without derivative, *Tokio Math. Ges.* **1** (1903), 176–177. Electronically available at <https://doi.org/10.11429/subutsuhokoku1901.1.F176>
- [13] J. R. Trollope, An explicit expression for binary digital sums, *Math. Mag.* **41** (1968), 21–25.